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The interactive whiteboard supports joint focus in collaborative learning

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INTRODUCTION

The interactive whiteboard (IWB) has been an important educational tool at our institution for a long time, and since 2010, an innovative learning space consisting of group stations with IWBs, suited for collaborative learning has been available [1]. In the present paper, the term collaborative learning describes a specific kind of group work, in which students actively work together on the same task, where the intention is for the students to learn together [2]. The potential of collaborative learning is explored extensively in the literature [3] [4].

Throughout two terms of fall 2016 and spring 2017, students at a preparatory physics course for engineering education attended weekly collaborative learning sessions in an innovative learning space. The intention was to use the IWB as a joint focus for both the students and the teachers, thus facilitating a collaborative learning process. One study has indicated three ways in which the IWB may facilitate collaborative learning processes in physics: Exploratory processes, characterised by collaborative brainstorming and sketching on the IWB; Explanatory processes, where one student takes on a teacher's role towards the rest of the group, using the IWB; and Clarifying processes, which were characterised by inquiries or clarifying questions to what had been written on the IWB [5]. The same study also indicated a fourth work process, which did not facilitate collaborative learning: Insertion, which was characterised by one student inserting a solution on the IWB already sketched on paper, while the rest of the group either sat quietly observing or were busy working individually. In the present study, a paperless work procedure was introduced, with the intention of minimising this latter work process, i.e., to have the students work as a group and not just *in* a group.

Although collaborative learning represents a student-centred learning context, the involvement of the teacher(s) plays a crucial role in the success of the students' learning process and their learning outcome [6]. This calls for careful considerations regarding the intention of the group work, the design of the group work and the tasks that are to be solved, the assessment of the group work process and product (i.e. solutions). The teacher also needs to consider how to provide support and guidance during the group work. Regarding the latter point, the success of teacher interventions depends on the teacher's ability to adapt his or her feedback to the students [7], which furthermore depends on the teacher's insight into the students' needs [8]. In this case, the IWB may facilitate easy insight, due to its sheer size.

In this paper, we present results from focus group interviews with students participating in these collaborative learning sessions. The results reflect the students' perspective, concerning the role of the IWB, how the IWB may affect the collaborative learning process, and the teachers' role as perceived by the students.

1 BACKGROUND

1.1 The preparatory physics course for prospective engineering students

In the preparatory physics course, the description of learning outcomes states the importance of carrying out experiments, doing measurements and interpret the results. Another aspect is the importance of oral skills, stated as: "*The candidate can communicate with others about natural science issues using physical concepts and sizes*" [9]. In traditional classroom teaching the learning outcomes mentioned above have been an important part of the course. However, to extend and develop the student activity even further, new innovative teaching and learning methods were

introduced. An important part of the changes was an extensive use of collaborative learning.

In this context, it was crucial to increase the “teacher density”, i.e. double the amount of supervisors present when the students were active and needed feedback. This was done without adding extra resources, but through a change of how the classes and the course were organized. Instead of giving two student groups, at approximately 45 students each separate lectures, they received joint lectures from one of the two teachers, followed by separate student-active learning sessions where both teachers were present. Each week the students had two lectures that were followed by student-active sessions. One of these sessions was held in the innovative learning space, which is the focus of this paper. Participation in these sessions was voluntary.

As a consequence of the structural and pedagogical changes that were introduced, it was natural for the teachers to work collaboratively. This collaboration included not only the planning of the time schedule, but also the planning of the active learning sessions and the lectures. The teachers together reflected upon the design of the activities, how they were perceived, and to what degree the intended learning outcome was realised. Through this collaboration, new innovative teaching and learning methods were developed throughout the year.

1.2 The innovative learning space

The innovative learning space consists of group stations, each equipped with an IWB that supports electronic data logging, typing and handwriting. This makes it easy to write formulas and do calculations similar to how one would do it on paper or on a whiteboard, but with the possibility of saving it. Sound reducing curtains form separated work stations for up to four students, see *Fig. 1*, where the innovative learning space is shown with and without use of the curtains.

Fig. 1. The innovative learning space with and without curtains around the group stations.

1.3 Collaborative and active learning

The lecture and the subsequent session in the innovative learning space dealt with the same physics topic. The constellations of the groups were decided by the teachers, and were changed frequently. Two teachers were supervising and facilitating discussions within the groups.

The regular working routine in the innovative learning space consisted of the students: logging into the pc at the work station, downloading the file of the day from the learning management system, and performing the tasks. At the end of the

session, the file was uploaded in order to be shared with the teachers and the group. The tasks were written in the same software as used in the lectures.

On the IWB, the students read the task, monitored the experiments, calculated, and wrote their comments and results. This led up to the IWB as a joint focus for the group and made it possible for the students and the teachers to work completely paperless. During sessions, the only “papers” present were textbooks and formulas. *Fig. 2* shows examples from these student-active learning situations.

Fig. 2. Students working in the innovative learning space.

2 DESIGN OF TASKS FOR THE INTERACTIVE WHITEBOARD

Through the design of the tasks, it is possible to facilitate use of the IWB as a joint focus for collaborative learning. Every session included practical exercises and measurements of physical quantities, which were mostly done by use of sensors and a data logging software. The experimental graphs and results were copied into the file and subsequently discussed, or calculations were done based on the measured values.

An example of how a practical task may look like is shown in *Fig. 3*, where Newton's first law is explored in two-dimensions by decomposition of three forces pointing in various directions. The picture to the left in *Fig. 3*, shows a page in the downloaded file, while the picture to the right shows the uploaded file. In this task, a photo is inserted to illustrate how the practical exercise should be done. In addition, short itemized sentences explain the idea. The group has copied a segment from the data logging software and done further calculation on the measured values in order to accomplish this task. The results are written by hand into the file.

Praktisk oppgave: Summen av krefter

- Tre personer drar i hver sin kraftmåler.
- Snorsystemet skal være i ro.
- Tegn x,y-akser på gradskiven.
- Mål kreftene ("Digits" i Capstone) og vinklene.
- Dekomponer kreftene og regn ut ΣF_x og ΣF_y

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1	270°
2	150°
3	70°

$F_{x2} = F \cdot \cos 20^\circ = 43,8 \text{ N} \cdot \cos 20^\circ = 41,2 \text{ N}$
 $F_{y2} = F \cdot \sin 30^\circ = 21,2 \text{ N} \cdot \sin 30^\circ = 10,6 \text{ N}$

Fig. 3. A task before and after the students have answered using the interactive white board.

Another way of facilitating for use of the IWB is shown in *Fig. 4*. Here an ordinary textbook exercise has been modified into an IWB version. The task has been rewritten from “What is the spring constant?” to the more open question “Investigate whether the spring obey Hooke’s law. If so, estimate the spring constant”. The more open questions are intended to induce discussions of concepts, instead of merely calculating answers.

Fig. 4. A textbook exercise to the left changed into an interactive white board version to the right.

The reason for the changes done was to prevent the students from solving the task individually in their own notebooks instead of together as a group. By preparing ready-made graphical backgrounds, tables etc. in the task files, the intention was to make it more attractive for the students to use the IWB instead of paper.

Furthermore, open spaces are left in the files making room for the students to write their answers. In *Fig. 4* for example a system of coordinates has been prepared, in order to provide an effective learning session, where the focus is on the physical problems and concepts, not on technical details.

3 THE STUDENTS' PERSPECTIVE

Data was collected through three focus group interviews with some of the participating students, towards the end of the last term (two male student groups and one female student group, in total ten students). The students were interviewed about their perceptions and experiences with the sessions in the innovative learning space with an emphasis on the following themes: the IWB, the group work process, and the teachers' role. An independent researcher conducted the interviews, which each lasted between 70 and 100 minutes. The transcribed interviews have been read by all authors through several iterations, in order to obtain a consistent impression on the themes described above. Overall, the students perceive the learning sessions as valuable, albeit for different reasons. Some students emphasise the importance of practical tasks, while others put emphasis on the conceptual problems. Most of the students seem to appreciate the collaborative aspect of the learning sessions.

3.1 The interactive whiteboard

From the teachers' perspective, the intention with the IWB was to facilitate a joint focus for the students, thus contributing to collaborative learning. The students very much seem to have recognised and appreciated this:

Male1Group1: Everything takes place on the board, the board is crucial. It is somehow the whole point of being there.

Female1: You look at the same thing, you are working together. Remove it, and you only have a regular group room with students who work on their own task. [...] it makes people work together.

Male1Group2: [...] everyone is paying attention to what is happening on the board, nobody is sitting at the corner of the table and calculating on their own. It «sticks» the group together.

Male2Group1: [...] the big board helps to see what is going on. Yeah, and that everyone sees it. We do everything together.

All student groups mention experiences with technical difficulties writing on the IWBs. However, while this has been a cause for some frustration, the students seem to have gotten accustomed to these difficulties.

3.2 Group work process

The students seem to perceive the IWB as an important part of the group work, due to its affordance as an area of joint focus. As we see it, this has some positive effects on the students' group work process. Several students mention that the group-work situation makes them endure difficult physics problems longer, compared to situations where they work alone:

Male2Group1: If you meet a problem at home, it's easy to give up and do something else. The threshold is a little higher when you are here and can get help from the teacher or other students.

The main point of working collaboratively is to learn together, which is also reflected in the students' perspectives on the group-work situation. A key aspect here is an emphasis on conceptual problems, rather than mere calculations:

Male2Group1: [It] can be easier to understand when someone at your level talks about it rather than the teacher. Also if you sit there and do not understand something, there are three "teachers" who can teach you in three different ways.

Female1: [...] you learn so much by explaining to others what you have understood, and to get an input on what you have not understood yourself. So you get a complete picture, as long as everyone participates.

When it comes to solving problems on the IWB, all student groups mention the role of the student who is doing the actual writing on the IWB, albeit with various emphasis. On some occasions, this student is taking on a teacher's role, guiding the rest of the group through the problem solving. Opposite examples are also mentioned, where the group tries to guide the student writing on the IWB. If the student writing is somewhat informed about both the problem and elements of its solution, taking the role as a "secretary" is not seen as problematic. On the contrary, if everyone in a group is on the same level, this situation can cause fruitful discussions among the students. However, in the case where the student writing

feels uncertain or unknowledgeable about the problem altogether, the “secretary” role is seen as quite uncomfortable and not very fruitful for neither party in the group.

3.3 The teachers’ role

The students value the presence of two teachers, simply because it makes the teacher resource more accessible. The IWB plays a role with regard to teacher interventions, in the sense that the students’ solutions are immediately available. For the teachers, this availability helps providing concise feedback. The students seem to value the teachers’ approach when it comes to teacher interventions:

Male2Group1: [The teachers] are becoming a bit like a supervisor. When we ask for help, they do not only tell us how to do it, but say how we must think.

Female3: They spend more time with us in the innovative learning space [...] [Here] they have to sit down and ask themselves: “Why don’t they understand this?” [...] They use more time on each of us and I think they have started to see what people know [...] They are very good at remembering names [...] and have started picking up on how people work and how to approach them.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The intention of the sessions was to increase the student activity, where the IWB was a tool to facilitate effective collaborative learning, supported by the design of the tasks and the paperless work procedure. Experiences expressed by the students support the notion that this intention was realised. The IWB’s affordance as a joint focus for every participant in the student groups seems to yield some positive effects with regard to how the students structure their work process.

When the students referred to writing on the IWB they used the terms “teacher” or “secretary”. According to the students, the description of the “teacher” role is consistent with the explanatory, exploratory, and clarifying work processes, described in [5]. The “secretary” role may entail acting as a facilitator for the group, or mere dictation, where the student writing is not taking part in the problem solving. However, with reference to [5], none of the students expressed experiences consistent with the work process termed insertion. This is also in accordance with the observations by the supervising teachers.

Furthermore, the students appreciated the role of the teachers as supervisors and the importance of immediate feedback. This depended on “teacher density”, i.e. their presence and availability, and the precision with which they met the students’ needs. From the teachers’ perspective, the fact that they were two meant that they could provide effective supervision. Furthermore, because the students’ work was immediately available on the IWB, they were able to provide concise feedback, addressed to the entire group, as opposed to individual students.

The challenges expressed by the students mainly concerned the actual writing on the IWB. Even though the students expressed awareness of the learning outcome associated with acting as a “teacher” or “facilitator” in front of the others, they often found this position challenging, and even daunting, this was emphasised by the female students. This represents an aspect of the collaborative learning situation which will be subject to careful consideration in the future, given that the aim is to further realise the potential of collaborative learning.

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